

COPPER PLATING PROCESSES FOR SILICON HETEROJUNCTION SOLAR CELLS: AN OVERVIEW

A. Lachowicz, A. Descoedres, J. Champliand, A. Faes, J. Geissbühler, M. Despeisse, S. Nicolay, C. Ballif
 CSEM PV-center, Neuchâtel, Switzerland
 Email: agata.lachowicz@csem.ch

Different approaches for copper plating have been chosen for production of heterojunction (HJT) cells following two main criteria: reliability and cost. Proven technologies from semiconductor or PCB industry based on a metal seed layer and photolithography have been successfully implemented as well as new processes with patterned seed layer or printed seed grid together with a dielectric layer as plating mask. Further cost reduction, especially for patterning, is the goal of current research activities and even direct plating of narrow lines is being developed in order to fully eliminate patterning steps.

At CSEM a processing route with a sputtered seed layer and hotmelt inkjet patterning has been optimized and efficiency above 24.7% achieved on precursors from an industrial partner. Excellent module stability in extended TC and DH tests has been confirmed for interconnection with wires as well as with soldered ribbons.

Keywords: silicon heterojunction cells, copper plating, reliability

1 COPPER PLATING IN PRODUCTION OF HETEROJUNCTION CELLS

Several processing routes are proven in production of heterojunction cells. Standard technology from PCB and semiconductor industry including a metal seed layer and photolithography (fig. 1) has been adopted for solar cell production. Silevo has used dry film resist for production of tunnel oxide junction cells in the past [1], photolithography has been reported by Sunpreme recently [2].

Figure 1: Process sequence with sputtered seed layer and photolithography

Another approach is to use a layer of dielectric like silicon nitride or silicon oxide in order to prevent plating on the thin conductive oxide [3, 4]. An organic mask for patterning is avoided and the dielectric layer may stay on the cell and serve as a second antireflective coating, also allowing for thickness reduction of the TCO. The process sequence is depicted in figure 2. At first a PVD seed layer is deposited over the entire surface, a grid pattern formed by inkjet printing of a UV curable ink and the seed layer in between the grid etched away.

Figure 2: Process sequence with patterned seed layer and a dielectric layer as plating mask

In the next step a dielectric layer is deposited by PECVD over the entire surface. A removal of the UV curable ink with a solvent is still feasible in spite of the (thin) dielectric layer and at the same time the remaining seed layer grid is exposed. Copper plating can be carried out simultaneously for both sides with contacting at the busbars.

The advantage of this process sequence is the low consumption of the UV ink for patterning: only the grid area, less than 5% of the cell are covered by the organic ink. On the other hand additional PECVD equipment is needed, beside PVD for the seed layer, inkjet printer and plating line, which increases up-front investment.

Another process with a dielectric layer as plating mask is used by Kaneka in production [5]. The grid is formed by screen or inkjet printing of a silver paste. The dielectric layer is then deposited over the entire surface (fig. 3). Since the surface of printed fingers is rough the dielectric layer on top of the finger is not perfectly dense and the plating current can pass through. An annealing step after the deposition of the dielectric may enhance the defects in the layer above the printed fingers.

This process sequence is quite short, however the silver paste consumption needs to be kept very low in order to maintain a cost advantage in relation to standard screen printed metallization.

Figure 3: Process sequence with seed grid and a dielectric layer as plating mask

The share of plating in production is still very low, below 5% [6] with Sunpower having implemented plating for (diffused) IBC cells in production in GW range. Production of heterojunction cells with copper plating has started. Kaneka 40 MW, Sunprime: pilot line in 2018, 24% reached in production with copper plating, Tongwei: 100 MW production plating line in construction, GS-solar: 100 MW in construction and 500 MW planned [7].

Mostly the proven technology with seed layer and photolithography is used. A sputtered metal seed layer has several advantages: high lateral conductivity for uniform current distribution, low contact resistivity to thin conductive oxides and good adhesion. And it enables simultaneous plating on both sides of bifacial cells. Copper lines defined with photoresist have a rectangular shape and high aspect ratio.

2 BASELINE PLATING PROCESS AT CSEM

Our baseline process comprises a sputtered seed layer and patterning by hotmelt inkjet printing. Copper deposition occurs simultaneously on both sides. With a dedicated contacting unit the current can be set separately for both sides, with optimum current density for the respective grid layout.

Line dimensions of 25 μm height and width are reliably feasible with hotmelt inkjet patterning. The specific resistivity of lines deposited from our electrolytes is slightly higher than the resistivity of bulk copper, with values between 2.0 and 2.6 $\mu\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$. The contact resistivity is in the range 0.05 to 0.5 $\text{m}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ on ITO, dependent on the type of ITO or measured on different precursors from project partners. The adhesion on ITO is very good: 4 N/mm, measured in a 180° peel test on soldered ribbons.

Table I: Cell efficiency certified by ISFH CalTec. Monofacial cell with copper plated grid with 4 busbar layout, on a precursor from an industrial partner. Measurement with aperture.

Cell	Area [cm ²]	Jsc [mA/cm ²]	Voc [mV]	FF [%]	Eff [%]
4BB, monofacial	222.8	40.3	736.1	83.3	24.73

The achieved efficiency of 24.7% and 83.3% fill factor confirm the good quality of single process properties like contact resistance, line width and line conductivity and a good matching of all process steps (table I).

Excellent stability of modules with heterojunction cells with copper plated metallization has been confirmed for interconnection with wires (Smart Wire Technology) as well as for interconnection with soldered ribbons, exceeding in both cases three times the IEC 61215 norm. For more details on the process please refer to previous publications [8, 9].

3 COST COMPARISON

The consumption of the low-temperature silver paste for bifacial heterojunction cells is strongly dependent on interconnection. For standard soldering not only the lower specific conductivity of this low-temperature paste has to be compensated but also relatively thick busbars have to be printed in order to assure good adhesion after soldering. The paste consumption is above 300 mg for a bifacial cell with 5 busbars. Additionally the price for this paste is higher than for standard high-temperature paste. For the calculation the value 750 EUR/kg has been used (fig. 4, “SP 5BB + Soldering”).

Interconnection with an electrically conductive adhesive (ECA) allows for reduction of the silver paste as there is no need to print busbars, the ECA adheres very well on the TCO. Additionally light capturing ribbon (LCR) might be used. The cost for the ECA has to be added in the calculation for interconnection. Further reduction of silver paste consumption is feasible with the Smart Wire Technology (SWCT) [10].

For copper plating much higher up-front investment for equipment is necessary compared to screen printing but the cost for copper deposition is low. In the case an organic mask is used then the patterning has the highest cost share. For plating processes standard ribbon soldering is considered. In fig. 4 cost calculation for the sequence with sputtered seed layer and hotmelt inkjet patterning and for patterned seed layer with dielectric mask are shown.

For the calculation only equipment depreciation is included and the cost for materials, consumables and waste treatment. All costs influenced by local conditions like facility and labor are excluded.

Figure 4. Simplified cost calculation for metallization and interconnection for heterojunction cells using screen printing or copper plating and different interconnection schemes.

4 PROCESSES IN DEVELOPMENT

The main goal of research activities is to reduce the cost for patterning. One approach is to transfer a Nickel seed grid from a foil onto the wafer surface by laser. The wafer is covered by a dielectric layer like Al_2O_3 (ALD) or SiN_x (PECVD) to prevent plating on the TCO. The transferred nickel is sintered through the oxide layer by a second laser step. Pulse-reverse copper plating is used to minimize ghost-plating. Promising efficiency of 22.2% has been reported [11, 12].

Another interesting approach is to use a PVD seed layer stack with a metal on top, which forms a native oxide (e.g. Aluminum) and serves at the same time as plating mask. Different patterning methods including inkjet of an etching solution may be used to remove the native oxide on grid positions for plating. Reported efficiency: 20.2% [13]

With selective plating of copper lines directly on the TCO surface the patterning step could be fully eliminated. A dynamic meniscus of the Cu electrolyte is formed on the cell surface using micro-nozzles with additional confinement by air flow [14]. In order to maintain the dynamic meniscus the electrolyte flow speed has to be very high. Consequently the solution exchange at the wafer surface is very high enabling high copper deposition rates.

Further research activities at several institutes comprise e.g. electrodeposition directly on TCO or forming a seed layer selectively in the openings of a mask in order to improve the adhesion of plated layers.

5 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT ROUTES FOR COPPER PLATING ON HJT CELLS

A sputtered metal seed layer enables simultaneous plating on both sides of a bifacial cell, also in the case of busbar-less cells, beside other advantages as mentioned in section one. Patterning by photolithography is commonly used in high volume production of printed circuit board, however for solar cells even cheaper alternatives are wanted. Photolithography comprises three steps: resist application, imaging and development whereas with hotmelt inkjet printing the patterning occurs in one step. With both patterning methods fingers of rather rectangular cross section with high aspect ratio are formed.

In case of a dielectric layer as plating mask the finger width increases with plated finger height giving a rather round shape. This leads to wider lines than obtainable by photolithography. On the other hand the optical width in the module is significantly lower than the physical width through light recycling from reflection on the round finger surface [4].

For the cost calculation an additional PVD tool has been included for the seed layer deposition. It should be technically feasible to deposit the TCO and the metal seed in one equipment. Only an additional chamber and additional targets for the seed layer would be required and the up-front investment would be smaller.

6 SUMMARY

High efficiency and excellent module stability for HJT cells with copper electroplated metallization have been reported by several companies [2, 5, 15]. Mostly standard technology adopted from PCB production is used.

At CSEM a sequence with seed layer and one-step-patterning by hotmelt inkjet printing has been optimized and high efficiency and very good module stability also confirmed.

Research activities for cost reduction of patterning are ongoing. There are still technical obstacles, cell efficiency is rather moderate and reliability not proven.

High up-front investment and the introduction of new technologies slow down the implementation of copper plating in production, while the silver price is low.

Today the silver consumption for PV accounts for more than 6% of the world silver supply [6]. The PV production capacity is supposed to increase from 109 GWp in 2018 to between 200 and 500 GWp in 2025 [6] and should further increase to terawatt levels in the next decades in order to meet the climate goals. The higher silver demand may lead to silver price increase and give an additional stimulus for copper plating.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program with funding of the DISC project under grant agreement N°727529 and with funding of the AMPERE project under grant agreement N° 745601.

We thank Choshu Industry Co. for providing us excellent HJT precursors for plating.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] J. Heng et al., >23.1% Efficiency Tunnel Oxide Junction Cell with Electroplated Cu Grid, 29th EU PVSEC, 2014
- [2] W. Ma et al., 24% Efficiency Hybrid Cell Technology Integrating a Low-cost Cu Metallization, IEEE, 2018
- [3] US patent number US000008236604B2, O. Schultz-Wittmann et al., Tetrasun, 2011
- [4] O. Schultz-Wittmann, High Volume Manufacturing of High Efficiency Crystalline Solar Cells with Shielded Metal Contacts, 32nd EU PVSEC, 2016
- [5] D. Adachi et al., Effect of SiO_x barrier layer prepared by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition on improvement of long-term reliability and production cost for Cu-plated amorphous Si/crystalline Si heterojunction solar cells, Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, 2017
- [6] International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic, ITRPV, 10th Edition, 2019, itrpv.net
- [7] Taiyang News Report Heterojunction Solar Technology, 2019
- [8] A. Lachowicz et al., Copper Plating Process for Bifacial Heterojunction Cells, 33rd EUPVSEC, 2017
- [9] A. Lachowicz et al., Review on Plating Processes for Heterojunction Cells, 8th Workshop on Metallization and Interconnection, 2019
- [10] A. Faes et al., Metallization and interconnection for high-efficiency bifacial silicon heterojunction solar cells and modules, Photovoltaics International, 2018
- [11] A. Rodofili et al., Laser Transferred Ni-seed for the Metallization of Heterojunction Cells by Cu Plating, 33rd EU PVSEC, 2017
- [12] Y. Franzl et al., Optical Evaluation of Laser Generated Plating Seed Layers, 8th Workshop on Metallization and Interconnection, 2019
- [13] T. Hatt et al., Native Oxide Barrier Layer for Selective Electroplated Metallization of Si HJT Cells, Solar RRL, 2019
- [14] M. Balucani et al., New Selective Processing Technique for Solar Cells, 4th Metallization Workshop, 2013
- [15] O. Schultz-Wittmann et al., Fine Line Copper Based Metallization for High Efficiency Crystalline Silicon Solar Cells, 27th EU PVSEC, 2012